

Part II: Theoretical and Methodological Frameworks

The current research, as shown in this section, builds on certain foundational studies. The data analysis is based on a bi-layered theoretical framework I call the Stylistic-Semantic Translation Model. This newly formulated model, founded on the Descriptive Translation Studies and the Manipulation Theory (discussed hereafter), helps to frame a holistic strategy for comprehending the translation's issues as well as the mediator's interventions. I also give a preliminary explanation for the empirical techniques and strategies used in the study, as well as contextualizing the scope regarding analyzing the translation of the stylistic elements in the selected Francophone African novels: *Une si longue lettre* by Mariama Bâ and *L'Aventure ambiguë* by Cheikh Kane.

Analyzing an author's style in translation studies is more significant when it examines the complex interactions between the source text and its translated version, rather than considering style as a self-contained property of either the original or the translated text. Kirsten Malmkjær (among others) agrees that stylistic analysis within the context of translation should not be handled as an isolated feature of either the translated text or its source version. In emphasizing Jean Boase-Beier's words, Annalisa Federici acknowledges that the evaluation of the dynamic relationship between a literary translation and style is evidently challenging (4). And, in her "Translational Stylistics: Dulcken's Translations of Hans Christian Andersen" (2004), Kirsten Malmkjær recommends that the relationship between the target text and its original must be investigated through comparative methods (16). However, previously, stylistic analysis vis-a-vis the translation of "a source text and its translation" was rejected on principle by scholars like Mona Baker who, in his "Towards a Methodology for Investigating the Style of a Literary Translator" (2019), according to Annalisa Federici, affirmed that: "... a translator cannot have, indeed should not have,

a style of his or her own, the translator's task being simply to reproduce as closely as possible the style of the original" (60).

The present thesis intervenes in these debates to support the position that translation studies must equally take the style of the mediator into account in considering the mediator's presence/absence in a text. Analysis in this context will shift the focus of translation from being just a derivative practice to being a creative practice as well. In addition, this shift towards the aspects of creativity is important if we are to keep holding onto the view of Lawrence Venuti (among others) about the indispensability of the mediator's visibility in translation. What I stand to advocate for is neither to dismiss the authorial style nor the style of the translator: both are authors and should have their unique styles. However, I choose to follow Kirsten Malmkjaer in arguing that the translator should use his or her style in a way that best (re)presents the source text's writer's style in the translation (15).

a) **Descriptive Translation Studies**

Descriptive Translation Studies is one of the theories on which the perspective and the analysis of the current study are built. In her *Stylistic Approaches to Translation*, Jean Boase-Beier asserts that the invention of this descriptive model can be traced to both James Holmes (1988) and Gideon Toury (1980) (5). However, I opt to follow the methodology proposed by Gideon Toury (1995), based on the research questions.

The Descriptive Translation Studies of the theorist Gideon Toury has been used since the 1970s not with the aim of prescribing the way literary translations are expected to be done, but instead, describing literary translations "as they were done" (Vandaele 102). As a reaction against what Enaka Tanyitiku calls the existing theoretical prescriptive studies (7), which is the traditional prescriptive approach to translation theories, Gideon Toury invented the descriptive model as a

means of prioritizing the idea of norms in literary translations (Ben-Ari et al. 153, Toury, *Descriptive Translation* 200–204), the sociological constraints that help guide, shape, and regulate the translator’s behavior (Dolmaya 347). The argument is that the style of the translated version should correspond with “the genre, of the target language, or of the linguistic, literary, or cultural system into which the target text fits” (Boase-Beier, *Stylistic Approaches to Translation* 5).

A descriptive examination of the translations in the context of Gideon Toury’s model is not considered a mere comparative assessment of the original text and its translated version. Therefore, Gideon Toury (1995) suggests a three-stage methodology that should be observed in the systematic analysis of translations when applying Descriptive Translation Studies:

The analyst first selects target phenomena regarded as translational phenomena from the viewpoint of the target system. These translational phenomena are prior to, or independent of, the source text. In the second step, the analyst verifies these translational phenomena against the source text through a comparative analysis in the form of a problem/solution pattern. The purpose of this analysis is to establish translational relationships between source-text and target-text. Lastly, the third step consists of the reconstruction of the process of decision-making of the solutions for the respective problems (Tanyitiku 7).

From the explanation above, it is convincing that the Descriptive Translation Study ensures that translation is analyzed as a process, product, and function through the explanation (or description) of the translational phenomena. The process, as claimed by scholars, implies the thought process of the mediator, while the product is the texts “involved in the translation event.” The function in this context is the what, where, when, and why of the translations as well as the effects of the translations on the target audience (Ferreira and Schwieter 25).

Gideon Toury's model is a tool for the analysis of this study and therefore serves as part of the foundations for the bi-layered Stylistic-Semantic Translation Model. First, from the selected novels, I will identify and explain observable stylistic regularities/patterns present in the selected target novels, considering their acceptability. Then I will juxtapose these target translational phenomena with the respective source texts with a view to detecting changes that occur in the translation and possible challenges resulting from translating the authorial style, as well as identifying the strategies used by the translator. Finally, I will attempt to reconstruct possible effects of the translations on the target audience and propose possible solutions where needed.

b) Manipulation Theory

The Manipulation Theory is the second theory that supports the main arguments of the current thesis. In the 1980s, Descriptive Translation Studies gave birth to Manipulation Theory, which explicitly holds the claim that the translated text is a result of some sort of manipulation by the mediator (Hermans, *The Manipulation* 11). The Manipulation Theory is a school that emphasizes the view that a perfect translation remains impossible since the mediator, for certain reasons, will "inevitably mix noise in the translation." Lefevere then popularizes this theory of translation as a rewriting literary manipulation, by justifying various purposes that could lead the mediator to manipulate the source text (Yu and Hongying 412).

The Manipulation Theory holds a claim that a writer's style, in the translation process, undergoes certain levels of manipulation. And in this view, the translator as a mediator is considered a manipulator for rewriting a source text. In the 1990s, Susan Bassnett collaborated with André Lefevere in expounding this Manipulation Theory, in their *Translation, History, and Culture*, as they came up with what is now popularly known as the Cultural Turn. The Cultural Turn tends to emphasize the role of translation in cultural development, thereby indicating the shift

of translation studies from text to culture (Yu and Hongying 412). The term implies a drastic movement from the initial focus of the field, which is textual and linguistic concerns, to an interdisciplinary focus. The term defines translation as a cultural construct and an act that relates to and impacts cultures and identities.

The interdisciplinary nature of this theory, from the perspective of Susan Bassnett and André Lefevere (1990), embraces insights from various fields like the postcolonial field, feminist discourse, ideology, etc.; it tends to provide an inclusive platform for diverse discourses. It is worth mentioning that the Manipulation Theory is not a theory opposing Descriptive Translation Studies (Snell-Hornby 50). They are complementary rather than contradictory to each other. In my analysis, therefore, I will identify and consider every possible factor capable of affecting the cultural mediator in translating certain elements of style in the chosen Francophone African texts.

c) Towards a Holistic Approach to Stylistic Translation Analysis

The current study derives a new bi-layered theoretical framework—Stylistic-Semantic Translation Model—that builds on and complements the existing theories of translation, especially the ones discussed above. The Stylistic-Semantic Translation Model accentuates that style is distinct from, yet interwoven with, semantics. Style, in this context, encompasses certain linguistic and artistic choices and connotative nuances. Semantics, on the other hand, involves the understanding of the meaning, the content, and its significance displayed through propositions.

This model does not treat style as a secondary element to meaning in a text. More importantly, it conceptualizes style and semantics as intertwined forms. These forms, therefore, are regarded as two layers, emphasizing that every translation—either implicitly or explicitly—deals with the negotiation of the two layers. As an innovative application, stylistic elements are first

identified and analyzed distinctly from the semantic features before discussing their interactional relationships in the translation. To this extent, I propose the following methodology:

1. Stylistic analysis: The first step involves analyzing the stylistic elements in the source text, then examining how these are presented in the translation.
2. Semantic analysis: This is the analysis of the stylistic features—within a semantic context—across both the source and the target texts.
3. Stylistic-Semantic Interaction: Here, both stylistic and semantic nuances are brought into dialogue. A comparison is made between both texts, with attention to justifying, describing the translation, rather than prescribing it.
4. Mediator's Impact: This is the final phase in the Stylistic-Semantic Translation Model. It examines the mediator's interventions between both cultures: how the original culture is (re)presented in the newly created text, and the possible impression the target reader could get from the source culture. The stylistic-semantic interaction between the different texts does not happen on its own: an agent is responsible for the various negotiations taking place. Even the interpretations of the original evolve the more the source text is revisited, leading to frequent intervention and rewriting. This model advocates, in reference to Lawrence Venuti, that the mediator's presence should be equally recognized as that of the original author (*Invisibility* 8). Building on ideas first developed by Antoine Berman in *The Experience of the Foreign: Culture and Translation in Romantic Germany* (1992), Lawrence Venuti, throughout his *Rethinking Translation. Discourse, Subjectivity, Ideology* (1992) and *The Translator's Invisibility: A History of Translation* (2008) claim that the translator as a mediator has two different options: one, the mediator can domesticate the original text. This could be a way of blending the source text into the everyday language

of the target audience. The second option is that the mediator can foreignize the source text. One of the ways to achieve this could be by choosing to keep the foreignness of such text through a more literal translation. The concepts of domestication and foreignization are what linguists claim to be the macro translation strategies (Ferreira and Schwieter 233). The translators of the chosen Francophone African novels tend to choose one of these options at a time to translate the original author's style into English. In the analysis, I will show whether the translation strategy used by the mediator is domestication or foreignization. Applying either of the two strategies in stylistic translation will have one effect or the other on the intended community. At the end of the analysis, I discuss the possible implications of the mediator's stylistic choices for the English-speaking audience: how the text-translation is possibly understood and received by the target community.

d) Data, Data Collection, and Data Analysis

I classify the data I will be analyzing in this study into two categories: primary and secondary data, which give me an original scope considered the basis of my study. The primary data are collected from the two selected source texts and their translations: 1) *Une si longue lettre* by Mariama Bâ, published in 1980 by Nouvelles Éditions Africaines du Sénégal, translated as *So Long A Letter* by Modupe Bode-Thomas; and 2) Cheikh Kane's *L'Aventure ambiguë* (1961), published by Julliard, translated as *Ambiguous Adventure* by Katherine Woods. The two Francophone African novels are chosen based on the unique stylistic devices employed by these Francophone African authors in addressing the various, crucial themes of their works.

My focus in the analysis of the texts mentioned above is on the stylistic figures present in these novels and how they are translated, with or without success. The excerpts from these novels (for analysis) will fundamentally consist of certain translational phenomena of the styles used by

the authors. The excerpts are chosen based on a comparative approach through the methodology of Descriptive Translation Studies, assessing how style is manipulated or preserved. Each excerpt represents an example of translational phenomena that show certain challenges in translating style. Overall, the chosen excerpts cover several issues relevant to cultural mediation, including the addition or omission of certain stylistic nuances and semantic adaptation or preservation. For my analysis, I will be referring to the first text (*Une si longue lettre*) as Bâ ST1. Its English version (*So Long A Letter*, by Modupe Bode-Thomas) will be referred to as Bâ TT1. The second source text (*L'Aventure ambiguë*) will be referred to as Kane ST2, while I will refer to its English version (*Ambiguous Adventure*, by Katherine Woods) as Kane TT2.

Secondary data come from the sources that study, critique, and interpret the primary data and theories discussed in this research. The secondary data form the bedrock on which this thesis is founded; these sources contribute to the validity of the work. In this corpus-based descriptive research, I analyze the qualitative data collected from the chosen texts previously discussed.

The analysis is based on the Stylistic-Semantic Translation Model, whose steps account for stylistic analysis, semantic analysis, stylistic-semantic interface, and the mediator's impact. The model ensures that the stylistic feature is clearly identified in the original text; it shows how it is modified or retained in the translated version; then it defines the reception of the target text, and how much the mediator's presence or absence is felt in the product. In order to detect possible shifts between the original texts and their target versions, chosen excerpts are compared with their respective translations in the English language. From the data collected from the selected Francophone African novels, the translational phenomena of the authors' styles appear as culture-bound terms, repetition patterns, musical/rhythmic effects, gender-specific/gender-neutral languages, and punctuation.

After identifying these stylistic figures, I evaluate the possible linguistic/cultural issues that arise in the process of translating these stylistic elements. This is followed by identifying the strategies that the mediator employs to convey these Francophone African authorial styles into English. And, the translation strategies, as claimed by Enaka Tanyitiku, refer to the “operational norms” (4) that represent the various methods applied by the mediator in translating stylistic figures in a literary translation.

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